

very safely that the observed higher than the spin-only values of the magnetic moments of the complexes might be due to the ferromagnetic interaction⁶.

All ligands show bands in the ν_{OH} regions. The absence of ν_{OH} in all the complexes indicate the removal of phenolic proton on coordination. The low energy shifting of ν_{C-S} in all the complexes suggests the participation of sulphur in coordination. ν_{C-N} (1570 cm^{-1}) remains unaltered on complexation⁶. This suggests that the nitrogen of the azomethine is not involved in the coordination. The high energy shifting of ν_{C-O} suggests the presence of oxygen bridging in the complexes⁷. The observed low energy shifting of ligand band at $\sim 1490\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and high energy shifting of band at $\sim 1300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicate the decreased bond order of C=S and increased bond order of C-N. The presence of an additional band at $\sim 960\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes may be due to ν_{N-N} ⁸. This suggests the N-N bond elongation and C=N bond formation^{9,10}.

On the basis of the above physicochemical studies, the following general structure may be given for the complexes.

where B = *o*-, *m*-, *p*-toluidine.

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Studies on Some Hydrazones, Semicarbazones, Thiosemicarbazones and Oximes as Ligands.

Part—IV : Some Divalent Metal Complexes

of Benzalacetone-Semicarbazone and Dibenzalacetone-Semicarbazone

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IN the programme of studies on Schiff's base complexes, complexation behaviour of bi-, tri- and tetradentate ligands have been reported earlier¹⁻⁵. It was thought worthwhile to have a comparative study of the complexing abilities of hydrazones, semicarbazones, thiosemicarbazones and oximes towards the transition metal ions. As a part of this programme, complexes of benzil phenyl hydrazone, 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone and oxime have been reported⁶⁻⁸. This communication presents some complexes of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn and Cd salts with benzalacetone and dibenzalacetone semicarbazone as ligands prepared with a view to study the effect of substituents on the complexing ability.

Experimental

Ligands were prepared by a known conventional method⁹. Ethanolic solutions of different metal salts were reacted with the ligand in 1 : 2 proportion and the solution refluxed for 30 min to 1 hr. Solutions were concentrated in a rotary vacuum evaporator and kept standing in a refrigerator when crystalline compounds separated out. In some cases addition of petroleum ether was necessary for the isolation of the complexes. These were filtered under suction, washed with absolute ethanol and ether and dried *in vacuo*. Metal, halogen, thiocyanate and nitrogen were estimated as reported^{6,7} earlier. Conductance was measured in $10^{-3}M$ acetone solution of complexes using Toshniwal conductance bridge. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made over solid specimens by Gouy method. Infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer-671 spectrophotometer. Visible electronic spectra were recorded in $10^{-3}M$ chloroform solution of the compounds using Hilgerwatt Uvispeck spectrophotometer. Relevant analytical data are presented in Table I.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes belong to the general composition MLX_2 or ML'_2X_2 and ML_2X_2 , where L is

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NOTES

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compounds (Colour)	Δ_M mhos. cm ²)	μ_{eff} B.M.	% Halogen, thiocyanate or nitrogen		Electronic spectra ν_{max} in kK(e)
			Found (Calcd.)	Found (Calcd.)	
MnL(NCS) ₂ (Light yellow)	10.5	5.9	15.02 (15.26)	32.38 (32.23)	20.3(1), 22.5(1.5) 24.5(2)
MnL(NO ₂) ₂ (Light yellow)	12.8	5.8	14.71 (14.93)	19.08 (19.02)	—
CoL ₂ Cl ₂ (Orange)	8.4	4.9	11.32 (11.60)	13.76 (13.98)	18.5(36), 19.8Sh
CoL ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂ (Orange)	10.6	5.0	9.15 (9.27)	13.32 (13.20)	19.5(38), 20.1Sh
CoL ₂ (NO ₂) ₂ (Brown)	8.8	5.0	10.31 (10.50)	19.78 (19.97)	—
NiL ₂ Cl ₂ (Green)	12.5	3.1	11.22 (11.56)	13.65 (13.98)	9.6(6) 13.7(6) 24.9(16)
NiL(NCS) ₂ (Brown)	9.8	—	16.28 (16.14)	31.71 (31.89)	—
NiL ₂ (NO ₂) ₂ (Green)	9.2	2.9	10.22 (10.47)	19.85 (19.97)	—
[(NiL ₂)](ClO ₄) ₂ (Deep yellow)	248	—	9.38 (9.24)	13.42 (13.21)	18.0(60)
CuL ₂ Cl ₂ (Green)	6.8	1.81	12.21 (12.40)	13.81 (13.85)	15.4(39)
CuL(NCS) ₂ (Yellow)	7.4	1.79	17.11 (17.24)	31.15 (31.85)	—
CuL(NO ₂) ₂ (Yellow)	7.8	1.82	16.58 (16.87)	13.22 (13.59)	17.3(25)
ZnLCl ₂ (White)	10.2	—	20.42 (20.08)	21.68 (21.80)	—
ZnL(NCS) ₂ (White)	10.5	—	17.31 (17.65)	31.35 (31.32)	—
[(ZnL ₂)](ClO ₄) ₂ (Light yellow)	245	—	10.25 (10.17)	13.32 (13.08)	—
CdLCl ₂ (Light yellow)	12.5	—	30.01 (30.18)	19.28 (19.06)	—
CdL(NO ₂) ₂ (Light yellow)	10.3	—	26.15 (26.42)	16.22 (16.46)	—
[(CdL ₂)](ClO ₄) ₂ (White)	252	—	16.11 (16.30)	12.01 (12.18)	—
MnL'(NCS) ₂ (Light yellow)	10.8	5.8	11.71 (11.89)	25.26 (25.11)	20.8(1), 22.5(2) 24.8(2)
MnL'(NO ₂) ₂ (Light yellow)	8.5	6.1	11.43 (11.69)	14.72 (14.90)	—
MnL'(ClO ₄) ₂ (Light yellow)	10.4	6.2	10.98 (10.08)	7.55 (7.71)	—
CoL'Cl ₂ (Green)	12.5	4.5	13.72 (14.0)	16.58 (16.86)	19.5(32) 20.0
CoL'(NO ₂) ₂ (Blue)	8.6	4.4	12.11 (12.43)	14.58 (14.77)	—
CoL'(ClO ₄) ₂ (Blue)	11.7	4.5	10.52 (10.74)	7.32 (7.65)	16.5(300)
NiL'Cl ₂ (Deep yellow)	6.8	—	13.76 (13.95)	16.61 (16.88)	15.5(60)
NiL'(NCS) ₂ (Deep yellow)	11.5	—	12.28 (12.61)	24.49 (24.91)	—
NiL'(NO ₂) ₂ (Deep brown)	10.2	—	12.14 (12.39)	14.51 (14.77)	15.8(58)
CuL'Cl ₂ (Light green)	8.4	1.82	14.68 (14.93)	16.38 (16.68)	14.5(35)
CuL'(NO ₂) ₂ (Light yellow)	7.5	1.82	13.01 (13.28)	14.32 (14.63)	—
CuL'(ClO ₄) ₂ (Light yellow)	8.2	1.79	11.22 (11.48)	7.31 (7.59)	17.2(28)
ZnL'Cl ₂ (Light yellow)	6.5	—	15.48 (15.30)	16.38 (16.61)	—
ZnL'(NCS) ₂ (Yellowish white)	7.1	—	13.68 (13.84)	24.31 (24.56)	—
ZnL'(ClO ₄) ₂ (Yellowish white)	8.2	—	11.51 (11.77)	7.38 (7.56)	—
CdL'Cl ₂ (Yellowish white)	8.5	—	23.38 (23.69)	14.81 (14.97)	—
CdL'(NCS) ₂ (Yellowish white)	10.4	—	21.35 (21.64)	22.01 (22.33)	—
CdL'(NO ₂) ₂ (Yellowish white)	11.2	—	21.46 (21.31)	13.59 (13.27)	—

L = Benzalacetone semicarbazone.
L' = Dibenzalacetone semicarbazone.

benzal acetone semicarbazone, L' is dibenzal acetone semicarbazone and X is the anion. All the compounds are crystalline solids, have fairly low melting points and are soluble in acetone, in which medium the molar conductance values are low indicating their non-electrolytic nature. However, the zinc and cadmium perchlorate complexes of benzal acetone semicarbazone are exceptions and behave as 1 : 2 electrolytes.

Infrared spectra of benzal acetone and dibenzal acetone semicarbazone show main absorption bands at 3200, 1650-1670, 1600 and 930-950 cm^{-1} region assignable¹⁰ to $\nu(\text{NH})$, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{N}-\text{N})$, respectively. In the complexes, $\nu(\text{NH})$ remains almost unaffected excepting the cases where there is a possibility of hydrogen bonding with the anion (it shifts slightly to lower frequency region). $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ is observed at ~ 1630 – 1645 cm^{-1} , $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ around 1580-1600 cm^{-1} and $\nu(\text{N}-\text{N})$ around 945-970 cm^{-1} regions. Thus, shifting of the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ to lower frequency region indicates bonding through the carbonyl oxygen atom of the amide group and the azomethine nitrogen atom. Consequent upon bonding at these two sites $\nu(\text{N}-\text{N})$ shifts slightly to higher frequency region. Bonding has been further substantiated by the observation¹¹ of $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ around 460-480 and 320-335 cm^{-1} region, respectively.

In the thiocyanato complexes $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ is found at 2090-2100 cm^{-1} region suggestive¹² of the presence of N-bonded terminal thiocyanato group. In case of nitrate complexes, position of ν_1 and ν_4 bands around 1280 and 1420 cm^{-1} region and their difference $\Delta\nu$ of the order of 130 cm^{-1} indicated^{13,14} the presence of monodentate nitrate group. In zinc and cadmium and nickel perchlorate complexes of benzal acetone semicarbazone one broad band is noticed around 1100 cm^{-1} indicative^{15,16} of ionic perchlorate group in conformity with their conductance data. However, the other perchlorato complexes give rise to three distinct bands suggestive of the presence of coordinated perchlorato group.

In the uv region, the ligands show one band at ~ 520 nm which shifts in the complexes. In the visible electronic spectra of manganese complexes three absorption bands were observed around 20.3-20.8, 22.5 and 24.5-24.8 kK regions assignable¹⁷ to ${}^6\text{A}_1 \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_1(\text{G})$, $\rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_2(\text{G})$ and $\rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_1(\text{G})$ transitions, respectively indicating presumably a tetrahedral configuration. All the cobalt complexes of benzal acetone semicarbazone give rise to one absorption band around 18.5-19.5 kK region with a shoulder on the high frequency side attributable¹⁸ to ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ transition suggesting an octahedral configuration. Cobalt complexes of dibenzal acetone semicarbazone have one band at ~ 16.5 kK indicative of tetrahedral configuration. These assignments are consistent with their experimental μ_{eff} values (Table 1). Nickel chloride and nitrate complexes of benzal

acetone semicarbazone exhibit three absorption bands around 9.6, 13.7 and 24.9 kK region due to ${}^3\text{A}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{2g}(\text{F})$, $\rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F})$ and $\rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ transitions, respectively indicating a spin free octahedral configuration in conformity with their magnetic moment data. Nickel thiocyanato and perchlorato complexes show one broad band around 18.0 kK ($\xi=60$) region and all the nickel complexes of dibenzal acetone semicarbazone have bands around 15.5-15.8 kK. The spectral pattern and diamagnetic nature of the complexes are in agreement with a square planar configuration¹⁹. Copper(II) chloride complexes have one broad band at 14.5 and 15.4 kK suggesting²⁰ a distorted octahedral stereochemistry for this complex. In case of other copper complexes a band is noticed around 17.3-17.5 kK region presumably indicating a planar configuration for these complexes. On the basis of analysis, conductance and infrared spectral data, all the zinc and cadmium complexes have a possible tetrahedral environment around the metal ions.

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